

Online Appendix

Information and learning in coordination games: Theory and experiment

Zhiwei Cui¹, Xiaomeng Ding^{*2}, and Boyu Zhang²

¹*School of Economics, Renmin University of China, Beijing, China*

²*School of Mathematical Sciences, Beijing Normal University, Beijing, China*

A Analysis of Example 1–3

A.1 Analysis of Example 1

It is straightforward that there are only two absorbing sets \vec{A} and \vec{B} . It is sufficient to explore the perturbed dynamics.

Consider the absorbing set \vec{B} . Assume that agents $1, \dots, \lceil p^* s^{BR} \rceil$ play strategy A by mistake. Note that $\lceil p^* s^{BR} \rceil \leq s^{BR}$. Assume also that the information sample of agent $\lceil p^* s^{BR} \rceil + 1$ contains these $\lceil p^* s^{BR} \rceil$ A -players. Then, it is optimal for agent $\lceil p^* s^{BR} \rceil + 1$ to choose strategy A . Iteratively, strategy A can spread from the mutants $1, \dots, \lceil p^* s^{BR} \rceil$ to the whole population. In addition, it is easy to see that $\lceil p^* s^{BR} \rceil - 1$ or less mutations cannot induce the exit from the basin of attraction of \vec{B} . As a result, we have $c^{BR}(\vec{B}, \vec{A}) = \lceil p^* s^{BR} \rceil$. Following the same logic, we also have $c^{BR}(\vec{A}, \vec{B}) = \lceil (1 - p^*) s^{BR} \rceil$.

Given that $p^* < 1/2$, it holds that $c^{BR}(\vec{A}, \vec{B}) = \lceil (1 - p^*) s^{BR} \rceil \geq \lceil p^* s^{BR} \rceil = c^{BR}(\vec{B}, \vec{A})$. As an application of the Freidlin and Wentzell (1984) algorithm, $\mathcal{S}^{BR,*} = \vec{A}$ when $c^{BR}(\vec{A}, \vec{B}) > c^{BR}(\vec{B}, \vec{A})$, and $\mathcal{S}^{BR,*} = \vec{A} \cup \vec{B}$ when $c^{BR}(\vec{A}, \vec{B}) = c^{BR}(\vec{B}, \vec{A})$.

*Corresponding author

A.2 Analysis of Example 2

By the Proof of Proposition 3, there are two absorbing sets \vec{A} and \vec{B} , and $c^{IM}(\vec{A}, \vec{B}) = 2$ when $s^{IM} \geq 3$.

We first examine the case where $k \geq 2$ and $s^{IM} = 3$ or 4. It is sufficient for us to focus on the case where $s^{IM} = 4$. The other case where $s^{IM} = 3$ can be analyzed in a similar manner. Consider the absorbing set \vec{B} . Assume that agents 1 and 4 play strategy A by mistake. Assume also agents 1 and 2 are matched to each other and agents 3 and 4 are matched to each other. The B -players 2 and 3 receive the lowest possible payoff of d , while the two mutants receive a payoff of c . With positive probability, either of the B -players 2 and 3 observes the information of agents 1, 2, 3 and 4, and is motivated to switch to strategy A . Suppose also that agents 1 and 4 don't receive revision opportunities. Now we have agents 1, 2, 3 and 4 playing strategy A . Next, assume that agents 3 and 5 are matched to each other, and agents 4 and 6 are matched to each other. Following a similar reasoning as above, the B -player 5 may switch to strategy A . Iteratively, strategy A can spread to the whole population. Note also that a single mutation cannot induce the transition from \vec{B} to \vec{A} . Hence, $c^{IM}(\vec{B}, \vec{A}) = 2$. Given that $c^{IM}(\vec{A}, \vec{B}) = 2$, as an application of the Freidlin and Wentzell (1984) algorithm, $\mathcal{S}^{IM,*} = \vec{A} \cup \vec{B}$.

We next consider the case where $k = 1$ and $s^{IM} = 3$. Consider the absorbing set \vec{B} . Assume that agents 1 and 4 play strategy A by mistake. Following a similar reasoning as in the case where $k \geq 2$ and $s^{IM} = 4$, we may then have agents 1, 2, 3 and 4 playing strategy A . When $N = 6$, with a positive probability, agents 4 and 5 are matched to each other, and agents 1 and 6 are matched to each other. Following a similar reasoning as in the case where $k \geq 2$ and $s^{IM} = 4$, agents 5 and 6 will switch from strategy B to strategy A . In this case, we have $c^{IM}(\vec{B}, \vec{A}) = 2$ and $\mathcal{S}^{IM,*} = \vec{A} \cup \vec{B}$. However, when $N \geq 8$, strategy A cannot spread beyond agents 1, 2, 3 and 4. The reasoning is that each agent $i \in I \setminus \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$ can always observe a neighbor who playing strategy B and receiving the highest possible payoff of b . Thus, in this case, two mutations cannot lead to the exit from the basin of attraction of \vec{B} , i.e. $c^{IM}(\vec{B}, \vec{A}) > 2$. As an application of the radius-coradius theorem in Ellison (2000), $\mathcal{S}^{IM,*} = \vec{B}$.

A.3 Analysis of Example 3

By the Proof of Proposition 3, there are two absorbing sets \vec{A} and \vec{B} , and $c^{IM}(\vec{A}, \vec{B}) = 2$ when $s^{IM} \geq 3$.

First, consider the case where $s^{IM} = 3$. Consider the absorbing set \vec{B} . Assume that agents 1 and $N/2 + 1$ play strategy A by mistake. Assume also that agents 1 and 2 are matched to each other and agents $N/2 + 1$ and $N/2 + 2$ are matched to each other. The B -players 2 and $N/2 + 2$ obtain the lowest possible payoff of d , while the mutants 1 and $N/2 + 1$ receive a payoff of c with $c > d$. With positive probability, the B -player 2 observes the information of agents 1, $N/2 + 2$, and herself and is motivated to switch to strategy A . By the same reasoning, the B -player $N/2 + 2$ is also motivated to switch to strategy A . Iteratively, strategy A can spread to the whole population. The remaining part can proceed in the same manner as does the case where $k \geq 2$ and $s^{IM} = 4$ in Example 2.

Then, consider the case where $s^{IM} = 4$. In this case, every agent observes the information of all her neighbors. Consider the absorbing set \vec{B} . Assume that two agents play strategy A by mistake. Note that the ring network satisfies that for each agent, there exists no link among her neighbors.¹ As an implication, for each remaining B -player j , at least one of her three neighbors plays strategy B and is matched to a B -player. Then, these neighbors receive the highest possible payoff of b . Hence, agent j will continue to choose strategy B . Thus, $c^{IM}(\vec{B}, \vec{A}) > 2$. The remaining part can proceed in the same manner as does the case where $k = 1$ and $s^{IM} = 3$ in Example 2.

B Appendix: Experiments

B.1 Experimental Procedure

We conducted lab experiments at Beijing Normal University (BNU), China. We had two sessions for each treatment, where one session was at November 2022 and the other was at February 2023. The 330 subjects, primarily first-year undergraduate students from various disciplines at BNU, were recruited for the experiment. No subject was allowed to participate in more than one session. Subjects were randomly assigned to one of three treatments. The experiment was programmed by using the software oTree (Chen et al., 2016). Each session lasted about 1.5 hours. Subjects received a fixed show-up fee of 5 CNY (≈ 0.70 USD), and average earnings in the experiment were 71.99 CNY for T1, 71.67 CNY for T2, and 74.82 CNY for T3, with 1 game point=0.3 CNY.

Upon arrival at the lab, subjects were randomly assigned to seats. All of them consented

¹In the terminology of network science, the clustering coefficient is zero.

to the protocol, and nobody withdrew during the experiment. The subjects were not allowed to communicate privately. The experimenters read all instructions aloud, and subjects could ask questions at any time. In addition, subjects were given a black pen and a piece of blank paper to take notes or do calculations.

Table B.1 summarizes the experimental design. In rule test subjects needed to complete a questionnaire to ensure understanding of the game rules.² In lottery-choice task, subjects chose one of six lotteries to measure their attitude to risk. In beauty contest subjects were randomly divided into groups of five, and chose an integer between 0 and 100 (inclusive). In each group, the subject whose choice was closest to a half of the average of all members' choices was the winner and received additional rewards. The rewards would be divided equally when ties occurred. In survey subjects were asked to complete a questionnaire to collect basic demographic information and measure two personal characteristics. Subjects were informed that they were randomly (re)grouped to play all games (i.e. G1, G2, G3) and the beauty contest. To avoid habituation, the payoff matrix was transposed when a new phase started. At the end of each session, subjects were informed privately about the earning they obtained in each phase and the outcomes of lottery-choice task and beauty contest.

Table B.1. Experimental design.

Treatment	Phase 1	Phase 2	Phase 3
T1	rule test → G1	lottery-choice task → G2	beauty contest → G3 → survey
T2	rule test → G2	lottery-choice task → G3	beauty contest → G1 → survey
T3	rule test → G3	lottery-choice task → G1	beauty contest → G2 → survey

B.2 Experimental Instructions

The experimental instructions were written in Chinese, the native language of all the subjects recruited for the experiment. Here is the translated version of the instructions for T1. The instructions for other two treatments are similar and are omitted.³

B.2.1 Principles

Please keep quiet during the experiment, don't observe others' screens, and avoid computer operations irrelevant to the experiment. If you have any questions or need assistance, please

²In the experiment, we didn't number the rule test.

³We don't present the rule test to avoid redundancy.

raise your hand. We will come and help you.

The experiment is divided into several parts. Please read the instructions carefully before each part. Your earnings will be made up of two components: (1) a fixed show-up fee of 5 CNY, and (2) the number of points earned in the experiment, where the exchange rate is 1 point = 0.3 CNY. The earnings will be paid by bank transfer.

B.2.2 Instructions for G1

All subjects will be randomly assigned to different groups. Then, you will repeatedly play a game with 4 fixed neighbors within the group you belong to.

In each round, you will have two alternatives, A and B, and play with one randomly chosen neighbor. The number of points you will receive is determined as follows.

- If you choose A and your opponent chooses A, you will earn 3 points.
- If you choose A and your opponent chooses B, you will earn 0 points.
- If you choose B and your opponent chooses A, you will earn 2 points.
- If you choose B and your opponent chooses B, you will earn 2 points.

Fig. B.1. An illustration of the concepts of “neighbors” and “group”.

Once all members of your group have made their choices, you will automatically move on to the next round. Starting from the second round, you will see your choices and the number of points you received in the previous round.

This part lasts 30 rounds. Your earnings will be the sum of the points earned in each round.

B.2.3 Instructions for lottery-choice task

In this task you will choose one of six different lotteries. Each lottery has two possible outcomes, Head or Tail, with an equal probability (0.5 each). However, different lotteries give different

numbers of points for each outcome. Your earnings will be determined by the lottery you choose and its outcome. You will be informed of your earnings once all the games have finished.

Lottery	Head	Tail
No. 1	10 points	10 points
No. 2	15 points	8 points
No. 3	20 points	6 points
No. 4	25 points	4 points
No. 5	30 points	2 points
No. 6	35 points	0 points

Fig. B.2. Six lotteries in the task.

B.2.4 Instructions for G2

All subjects will be randomly reassigned to different groups. Then, you will repeatedly play a game with 4 fixed neighbors within the group you belong to.

In each round, you will have two alternatives, A and B, and play with one randomly chosen neighbor. The number of points you will receive is determined as follows.

- If you choose A and your opponent chooses A, you will earn 2 points.
- If you choose A and your opponent chooses B, you will earn 2 points.
- If you choose B and your opponent chooses A, you will earn 0 points.
- If you choose B and your opponent chooses B, you will earn 3 points.

Once all members of your group have made their choices, you will automatically move on to the next round. Starting from the second round, you will see your opponent's choices and the choices of another randomly selected neighbor the previous round, in addition to your choices and the number of points you received in the previous round.

This part lasts 30 rounds. Your earnings will be the sum of the points earned in each round.

B.2.5 Instructions for beauty contest

All subjects will be randomly divided into groups of five. Every subject will then choose an integer between 0 and 100 (inclusive).

In each group, the member whose choice is closest to a half of the average of all members' choices will be the winner and receive an additional reward of 15 points. The rewards will be

Part 3 In Progress

Round: 2	
Previous Round Your choice: A Your score: 0	The choices of two randomly chosen neighbors, including your opponent, in the previous round: Number of A choices: 1 Number of B choices: 1
Please make your choice in this round: <input type="radio"/> A <input type="radio"/> B	

Confirm

Fig. B.3. A screenshot of the computer interface regarding in G2.

divided equally when ties occur. You will be notified of your earnings once all the games have finished.

B.2.6 Instructions for G3

All subjects will be randomly reassigned to different groups. Then, you will repeatedly play a game with 4 fixed neighbors within the group you belong to.

In each round, you will have two alternatives, A and B, and play with one randomly chosen neighbor. The number of points you will receive is determined as follows.

- If you choose A and your opponent chooses A, you will earn 3 points.
- If you choose A and your opponent chooses B, you will earn 0 points.
- If you choose B and your opponent chooses A, you will earn 2 points.
- If you choose B and your opponent chooses B, you will earn 2 points.

Once all members of your group have made their choices, you will automatically move on to the next round. Starting from the second round, in addition to your choices and the number of points you received in the previous round, you will see your opponent's choices and the number of points they received, as well as the choices and points of another randomly chosen neighbor in the previous round.

This part lasts 30 rounds. Your earnings will be the sum of the points earned in each round.

Part 5 In Progress

Round: 2		
Previous Round Your choice: A Your score: 0	The choices and scores of two randomly chosen neighbors, including your opponent, in the previous round: (listed in ascending order of the scores)	
	choice	B A
	score	2 3
Please make your choice in this round:		
<input type="radio"/> A		
<input type="radio"/> B		

Confirm

Fig. B.4. A snapshot of the computer interface in G3.

B.2.7 Instructions for Survey

To avoid redundancy, we only present the questions relating to personal characteristics.

Question 1: If a game is played repeatedly, to what extent do you think that your current choices can influence your neighbors' future choices:

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

Question 2: You will choose one of two ways to receive your earnings for participating in this experiment:

- To receive full earnings in the first month after the experiment.
- To receive 30% of earnings in the first month after the experiment and 70% in the second month, with a 0.25 probability of receiving a 5 CNY bonus.

We will pay you according to your choice.

Table B.4. Determining factors of the use of updating rules ($\theta = 0.8$).

	All-Stag			All-Hare		
	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Phase 3</i>	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Phase 3</i>
NeighborsAction	1.866*** (5.05)	0.852** (2.28)	1.466*** (3.50)	-1.651*** (-4.14)	-1.808*** (-3.43)	-2.188*** (-2.65)
NeighborsPayoff	-0.151 (-0.49)	-0.969*** (-2.66)	0.615 (1.15)	0.083 (0.19)	0.495 (0.88)	-0.487 (-0.38)
RiskAttitude	0.192** (2.49)	0.065 (0.83)	0.333*** (3.23)	-0.249*** (-2.75)	-0.218* (-1.91)	-0.223 (-1.31)
Rationality	0.294 (1.35)	0.549** (2.38)	0.102 (0.36)	-0.327 (-1.21)	-0.175 (-0.51)	-0.296 (-0.57)
InfluenceBelief	-0.046 (-0.31)	0.591*** (3.95)	0.311* (1.70)	0.098 (0.54)	-0.627*** (-2.91)	-0.762*** (-2.64)
Patience	-0.169 (-0.60)	-0.071 (-0.26)	0.143 (0.39)	-0.606* (-1.86)	0.192 (0.45)	-0.010 (-0.02)
Final ⁻		0.929*** (3.03)	1.602*** (4.35)		-1.955*** (-4.03)	-1.731*** (-2.61)
Constant	-2.007*** (-2.74)	-2.677*** (-3.48)	-2.804*** (-3.12)	0.969 (1.16)	2.790*** (2.59)	2.581* (1.77)
Number of obs.	271	297	315	271	297	315
Pseudo R ²	0.138	0.100	0.219	0.159	0.182	0.304
LR chi ²	51.68***	37.14***	59.62***	47.54***	37.70***	36.61***
	WSLS3			WSLS2		
	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Phase 3</i>	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Phase 3</i>
NeighborsAction	2.260*** (3.54)	-0.166 (-0.50)	1.316*** (4.38)	-1.165*** (-3.31)	-1.280*** (-3.72)	0.181 (0.64)
NeighborsPayoff	0.442 (1.41)	-0.305 (-0.91)	0.261 (0.89)	0.206 (0.70)	0.070 (0.22)	0.455 (1.58)
RiskAttitude	0.019 (0.22)	-0.076 (-1.06)	0.085 (1.21)	-0.147* (-1.95)	-0.068 (-0.95)	0.003 (0.04)
Rationality	0.216 (0.92)	0.053 (0.26)	-0.085 (-0.43)	0.080 (0.38)	0.030 (0.15)	0.074 (0.39)
InfluenceBelief	-0.077 (-0.47)	0.347** (2.36)	0.128 (0.94)	-0.075 (-0.52)	-0.277** (-1.99)	-0.223 (-1.64)
Patience	0.192 (0.61)	-0.185 (-0.73)	-0.031 (-0.12)	0.403 (1.49)	0.017 (0.07)	-0.044 (-0.18)
Final ⁻		0.324 (1.14)	0.182 (0.68)		-0.308 (-1.09)	0.054 (0.21)
Constant	-3.221*** (-3.44)	-1.366* (-1.92)	-1.761*** (-2.72)	1.748** (2.50)	2.389*** (3.33)	0.886 (1.42)
Number of obs.	271	297	315	271	297	315
Pseudo R ²	0.119	0.029	0.087	0.060	0.059	0.017
LR chi ²	36.36***	11.49	37.61***	21.84***	24.39***	7.28

Notes: z-statistics in parentheses, *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Table B.5. Determining factors of the use of updating rules ($\theta = 0.9$).

	All-Stag			All-Hare		
	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Phase 3</i>	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Phase 3</i>
NeighborsAction	1.766*** (4.43)	1.000** (2.41)	1.209*** (2.75)	-2.030*** (-4.55)	-1.848*** (-3.28)	-2.229*** (-2.69)
NeighborsPayoff	-0.122 (-0.37)	-1.060*** (-2.66)	0.693 (1.23)	0.149 (0.32)	0.392 (0.65)	-0.513 (-0.40)
RiskAttitude	0.203** (2.44)	0.082 (0.93)	0.328*** (2.95)	-0.285*** (-2.84)	-0.188 (-1.51)	-0.213 (-1.23)
Rationality	0.400* (1.67)	0.551** (2.10)	0.081 (0.26)	-0.380 (-1.24)	-0.334 (-0.86)	-0.137 (-0.26)
InfluenceBelief	-0.074 (-0.45)	0.592*** (3.52)	0.446** (2.24)	-0.060 (-0.30)	-0.647*** (-2.70)	-0.728** (-2.46)
Patience	-0.278 (-0.91)	0.100 (0.33)	-0.075 (-0.19)	-0.462 (-1.28)	0.202 (0.45)	-0.117 (-0.18)
Final ⁻		1.131*** (3.35)	1.446*** (3.67)		-2.010*** (-3.85)	-1.897*** (-2.78)
Constant	-1.663** (-2.10)	-2.781*** (-3.25)	-2.769*** (-2.90)	1.908** (2.03)	2.882** (2.43)	2.615* (1.78)
Number of obs.	239	270	300	239	270	300
Pseudo R ²	0.137	0.112	0.207	0.205	0.184	0.317
LR chi ²	45.20***	35.53***	48.68***	53.91***	33.90***	37.76***
	WSLS3			WSLS2		
	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Phase 3</i>	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Phase 3</i>
NeighborsAction	2.015*** (3.12)	-0.239 (-0.68)	1.221*** (3.96)	-1.069*** (-2.78)	-1.511*** (-4.06)	0.223 (0.75)
NeighborsPayoff	0.493 (1.51)	-0.284 (-0.82)	0.238 (0.80)	0.267 (0.86)	0.278 (0.81)	0.561* (1.90)
RiskAttitude	0.029 (0.32)	-0.122 (-1.60)	0.047 (0.65)	-0.162** (-2.01)	-0.123 (-1.58)	0.020 (0.28)
Rationality	0.296 (1.21)	0.007 (0.03)	-0.084 (-0.41)	0.044 (0.20)	0.069 (0.32)	0.129 (0.64)
InfluenceBelief	-0.056 (-0.32)	0.330** (2.14)	0.176 (1.24)	-0.026 (-0.17)	-0.232 (-1.55)	-0.267* (-1.86)
Patience	0.216 (0.66)	-0.044 (-0.17)	-0.039 (-0.15)	0.327 (1.15)	0.026 (0.10)	0.021 (0.09)
Final ⁻		0.422 (1.43)	0.177 (0.65)		-0.336 (-1.12)	0.093 (0.35)
Constant	-3.112*** (-3.20)	-1.031 (-1.38)	-1.660** (-2.51)	1.586** (2.10)	2.504*** (3.22)	0.833 (1.28)
Number of obs.	239	270	300	239	270	300
Pseudo R ²	0.107	0.034	0.077	0.051	0.067	0.024
LR chi ²	30.23***	12.48*	31.64***	16.56**	25.21***	9.64

Notes: z-statistics in parentheses. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$